

HOUSEHOLD ENERGY CONSUMPTION PATTERN IN OGBOMOSO METROPOLIS, OYO STATE NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out to examine the households energy consumption pattern using the Almost Ideal Demand System(AIDS) MODEL in Ogbomoso Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. Primary data were collected from 200 heads of household through a multi-stage random sampling technique. The study reveals that kerosene is the most highly consumed energy source and the reason for preferring this energy source is its accessibility in the study area. AIDS estimation of demand functions using primary data indicates that demand for all forms of energy are price inelastic. Cross price relations indicate that kerosene is a substitute for both electricity and charcoal, where as electricity is a substitute for all the two. Charcoal and kerosene are complements. All the energy sources considered were found to have income elasticities less than one owing to the fact that energy consumption is a necessity. Government should provide electricity to most areas and there is need for pricing policy for energy such as kerosene.

KEYWORDS: Income elasticities; Energy; AIDS model

INTRODUCTION

Energy in the layman's language is often synonymous with strength or force or better still fuels. In technical terms, energy is that thing that can be used to produce work. Fuels and materials that ignite at moderate temperature burn with comparative rapidity and are obtainable in quantities of reasonable prices (William and Pinto, 2000.) Energy sources can also be classified as renewable and non-renewable forms. Renewable forms include; fuel, wood, solar energy, biogas and crop residue, while non-renewable forms are mainly petroleum products such as; kerosene, petrol, Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG) and coal. (Ajani, 1996).

The income level of individual influences fuel preferences and options that to some extent depend on the economic situation of the country considered. Technological advances and energy infrastructure also influence the cost, accessibility and affordability of different fuel options. Population growth and the rate of urbanization limited the access to any fuel other than fuel wood and these also exert pressure on both fuel wood supply and demand. Globally, over 2 billion people depend on firewood for cooking but 1.5 million of these have daily difficulty in finding sufficient supply. Increases in population have put pressures on the use of firewood to the point where its collection is destructive and unsustainable. (Bob, 1996).

Nigeria's economy has for over 2 decades now, been plagued by perennial energy crises, which manifest in at least 4 ways: erratic electric power supply, acute shortages of petroleum products on several occasions, sharp increase on energy commodities and frequent conflict between the populace, led by the labour movement, and the Federal Government on what should constitute appropriate prices of petroleum and other energy supplying commodities (CBN, 2000).

The World Bank (1993) attributed Nigeria's energy crises to: energy supply and distribution inadequacies; inappropriate energy pricing policies; inconsistent planning system and inadequate manpower and manpower training, among others. These findings point to the need for an urgent review of energy policies in Nigeria. More so those recent efforts by the Federal Government were aimed at encouraging inflow of foreign capital and private investment into Nigeria's energy sector.

Generally, African urban areas are associated with the use of modern fuels like electricity. However, the consumption of electricity depends on the adequacy of supply and the incomes of consumers. In cities with

rapidly growing populations, supply often gets limited. On one hand, declining economic conditions in most African countries limits investments in the generation of modern fuels. On the other hand, high population growth rates are not matched by economic growth. As a result, real incomes of urban residents are falling limiting their ability to afford the modern fuels. In fact, (Karekezi and Majaro, 2002) have noted that urban poverty in Africa is growing with the gap between the poor and the rich getting wider and the proportion of the poor getting bigger. Income distribution shows that most African urban households are poor. The poor tend to depend more on fuel wood to meet their energy requirements thereby contributing to the problem of deforestation. In most African cities, the most common energy source for low income people is fuel wood.

Household energy consumption can be defined as the energy consumed in homes to meet the needs of the householders (www.unescap.org). Energy consumption is the amount of energy consumed by a person or an apparatus shown as a unit (PHC.). Household energy can be categorized according to their usage, which includes charcoal, fuel wood, kerosene, electricity, biomass, animal dung, crop residues and gas etc.

Moreso, in the Northern part of Nigeria, urban area has higher rate of charcoal consumption for example, Borno region because apart for its use in space heating and ironing clothes, charcoal is widely used in homes to heat pieces of local scant sticks used as room air freshener. Between the year 1993 & 1994 which coincided with the period of acute fuel scarcity in Nigeria, rural household use less wood (as much as less as 25%) because the urban household which were hitherto using fossil fuels now had to rely more on wood because of availability and affordability (Alabe, 1994).

Charcoal usage is extensive during the harmattan season in Nigeria when it is used for domestic space heating purpose in addition to use as cooking fuel. Wood as firewood is used both in modern and traditional household and especially since the supply of other fuels is inadequate, irregular and or expensive. Consumption of firewood is however, not constant as it is also varies from time to time and from season to season for instance, more firewood is consumed during holidays when school children can participate in its collection and during the harmattan season when domestic hot water requirement is highest (Ajani, 1996). The key factors in the growth of household electricity consumptions are the number of household with access to electricity supply, penetration rate of electric appliances and the size and efficiency of appliances. Access to electricity varies widely among and within developing countries depending largely on per capita income and urbanization. Rapid growth in electrification rates in many countries reflects the impact of urbanization and rural electrification programmes (Ishiguro and Akiyama, 1995).

Urbanization is an important determinant of both the quantity and the type of fuel used in the developing countries. In general, urbanization leads to higher levels of household energy consumption. Although, it is difficult to separate the effects of urbanization from the increase in income levels that generally accompany urbanization. There is also a shift from traditional to commercial fuels and the factors that contribute to these include a decline in access to biomass fuel, inconvenience of transportation and storage and improvement in availability of commercial fuels in urban areas. Nevertheless, use of traditional fuels in many cities remains high among low income groups. The factors that contribute to these are a decline in the share of energy used for basic requirements such as cooking and lighting as income increases (Oladosu and Adegbulugbe, 1994).

With increasing disposable income and changes in life styles, households tend to move from cheapest to least convenient fuel (biomass) to more convenient and normally more expensive ones (charcoal, kerosene) and eventually to the most convenient and usually most expensive type of energy (LPG, natural gas, electricity). The key determinant of energy demand in the household sector includes; price of fuel and appliances, disposable income of household, availability of fuel and appliances and cultural practices (Leitmann, 1996). This paper has the objective of examining household energy consumption pattern in Ogbomoso metropolis of Oyo State, Nigeria with the view to estimate price (own and cross), expenditure and income elasticities.

METHODOLOGY

The study area is Ogbomoso metropolis Oyo State. Ogbomoso metropolis consists of two local government areas: Ogbomoso north and Ogbomoso south. The city is surrounded by three local government council which is Oriire, Ogo-Oluwa and Surulere local government areas (LGAs). The city is densely populated with an estimated population of 300,000 (2006 population census). Ogbomoso was estimated to cover 27.5 square kilometers and it is the second largest city in Oyo State, after Ibadan

Multistage stratified random sampling was adopted for the study. The study area was first stratified into two local government areas. In the second stage of sampling, 5 political wards were chosen in each LGA making a total of 10 wards. The last stage involve random selection of 20 respondents in each ward bringing the total number of respondents to be 200. Primary data were collected with the use of well-structured questionnaire. Data on household consumption expenditure pattern per month were collected on five-five days interval.

The Almost Ideal Demand System (AIDS) was used for the analysis. The Almost Ideal Demand System (AIDS) model of Deaton and Muellbauer (1980b) has enjoyed great popularity in applied demand analysis. Starting from a specific cost function, the AIDS model gives the share equations in an n -good system as

$$w_i = \alpha_i + \sum_{j=1}^n \gamma_{ij} \ln p_j + \beta_i \ln(X/P)$$

where w_i is the share associated with the i th good, α_i is the constant coefficient in the i th share equation, γ_{ij} is the slope coefficient associated with the j th good in the i th share equation, p_j is the price on the j th good. X is the

$$X = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i q_i$$

total expenditure on the system of goods given by in which q_i is the quantity demanded for the i th good. P is the price index defined by

$$\ln P = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \ln p_i + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \gamma_{ij} \ln p_i \ln p_j$$

in the nonlinear AIDS model. Deaton and Muellbauer (1980a) also suggested a linear approximation of the

$$\ln P = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \ln p_i$$

nonlinear AIDS model by specifying a linear price index given by that gives rise to the linear approximate AIDS (LA-AIDS) model. In practice, the LA-AIDS model is more frequently estimated than the nonlinear AIDS model.

Conservation implies the following restrictions on the parameters in the nonlinear AIDS model:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i = 1, \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i = 0, \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_{ij} = 0$$

Homogeneity is satisfied if and only if, for all i

$$\sum_{j=1}^n \gamma_{ij} = 0$$

and symmetry is satisfied if $\gamma_{ij} = \gamma_{ji}$

One advantage of the AIDS model is that the homogeneity and symmetry restrictions are easily imposed and tested.

Expenditure and price elasticities then can be derived easily:

$$\eta_i = 1 + (\beta_i / w_i)$$

$$\epsilon_{ii} = -1 + (\gamma_{ii} / w_i) - \beta_i$$

$$\epsilon_{ij} = (\gamma_{ij} / w_i) - \beta_i w_j / w_i$$

where η_i is the expenditure elasticity, w_i is the budget share of good i , ϵ_{ii} is the own price elasticity, and ϵ_{ij} represents the cross-price elasticity, in Marshallian terms (uncompensated).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Energy Used in Cooking

Kerosene is the largest in terms of the proportion of household consuming it in the study area. The ratio of household consuming kerosene is the highest followed by charcoal, electricity, firewood and sawdust at the aggregate level. This implies that the use of kerosene and charcoal is mostly common in the study area (Table 1).

Table 1: Energy Used in Cooking

Energy used for cooking	Frequency
Kerosene	200
Charcoal	139
Firewood	47
Sawdust	10
Electricity	72

Source: Field Survey, 2009.

B. Household preference for energy source

Household preference for a particular energy source is a function of several factor such as price, access, familiarity with the energy source, reliable supply, effectiveness etc. according to the findings compiled on households' preference for cooking fuels, accessibility stands out to be the major reason for a particular fuel to be the must preferred fuel. 101 out of 200 households attribute their preference to accessibility. Of all factors, accessibility, familiarity and effectiveness are the major factors although price is also a major factor (Table 2).

Table 2: Household preference for energy source

Reason for preference	Frequency
Cheap	53
Accessible	101
Reliable	22
Effectiveness	55
Familiarity	61

Source: Field Survey, 2009.

Total percentage greater than 100 due to multiple responses

C. Summary of Households Expenditure

The data in Table 3 shows that the overall expenditure is N10481.50k whereas energy expenditure is N1486.85k per month which accounts for about 14.2% of the average overall household expenditure. The expenditure share is 14.2%. This implies that energy budget is significant in the study area.

Table 3: Summary of Households Expenditure

Monthly Average Expenditure (in Naira)	Monthly Average Energy Expenditure (in Naira)	Expenditure Share of Energy (%)
10481.50	1486.85	14.2

Source: Field Survey, 2009.

D. Almost Ideal Demand System

Following Deaton and Muellbauer (1980a), the demand equation for each of the energy item was estimated without imposition of restrictions. The results of the analysis are presented in Table 4. From the table, the test of homogeneity was carried out. The result of the tests showed that in all the energy items, homogeneity condition is significantly violated. This result is in line with the findings of Deaton and Muellbauer (1980a); Ahmed and Shams (1994) and Awoyemi *et al.*, (2006).

Table 4 shows that all the Durbin – Watson statistics were within the plausible region. In all, one can effectively say that the dependent and independent variable have effectively performed their role.

In the first equation using the budget share of electricity as the dependent variable, it was clear that the entire variable were significantly at 1 per cent. This shows that as household expenditure price of kerosene and charcoal increases there is an increase in the budget share to electricity. There is also a direct relationship between the price of electricity and its budget share. A one per cent increase in the prices of kerosene and charcoal will lead to 0.02% and 0.05% increase in their budget respectively.

For kerosene as the second equation, three independent variables were significant which are the prices of electricity, kerosene and total energy expenditure respectively at 1% level. This shows that a 1 per cent increase in the price of electricity leads to a 0.05% increase in the budget share of kerosene in the home.

For charcoal as the third equation, three of the variables were significant at 1% and 5% respectively. The significant variables are prices of kerosene, charcoal and total energy expenditure. There is an inverse relationship between the price of kerosene and total energy expenditure and the budget share to charcoal

Table 4: Unconstrained parameter estimates and test of homogeneity

Commodity	Constant	Electricity	Kerosene	Charcoal	Expenditure	R ²	Dw
Electricity	-0.099 (-5.180)	0.034*** (11.419)	0.015*** (-3.389)	0.054*** (-3.002)	-0.0054*** (-15.479)	0.642	1.971
Kerosene	-0.191 (-3.140)	0.051*** (5.394)	0.053*** (3.662)	0.029 (0.524)	-0.0059*** (-10.985)	0.448	1.992
Charcoal	-0.174 (-4.257)	0.038 (0.586)	-0.002*** (-2.008)	0.043*** (11.241)	-0.006*** (-16.474)	0.683	2.072

Source: Field Survey, 2009.

E. Own Price and Cross Price Elasticities

Table 5 presents the full matrices of the own price and cross price elasticities. All the estimates of own-price elasticities except that of electricity conform to the law of demand with negative signs. It is surprising that the own-price elasticity for all energy items is below 1 in absolute terms. If the absolute value is considered, the lowest estimates of own-price elasticity for all the energy items are found in electricity (0.131), followed by kerosene (-0.150) and charcoal (- 0.462). This implies that the demand for the entire energy source is price inelastic. This result is not in line with the earlier finding by Gamtessa (2003) who reported price elastic for the entire energy source. From this table, electricity has the most inelastic own-price elasticity among other energy items considered on the study. This indicates that households in Ogbomoso metropolis are insensitive to changes in the price of electricity. That is if the price of electricity comes down or there is increase in the per capita income of household consumption will not be much affected.

Also, from the cross price elasticities, some of the estimated value had negative sign implying a complementary relationship. The rest of the estimated values had positive sign, which implies substitution effect. The result that electricity is a substitute for all forms of energy gives indication that the long-run option in ensuring energy transition is to harness the huge hydro-electric generation potential of the country

Table 5: Own Price and Cross Price Elasticities

Commodity	Electricity	Kerosene	Charcoal
Electricity	0.131	0.486	1.774
Kerosene	0.817	- 0.150	0.470
Charcoal	0.472	-0.020	-0.462

Source: Field Survey, 2009.

F. Elasticities for Energy Consumption

The mean budget share is considered in Table 6. The highest percentage of budget for energy went for charcoal 46.5% followed by kerosene 36.1% and electricity 17.4%

Expenditure elasticities of all the energy items are less than one. All the energy items are expenditure inelastic with electricity having the highest expenditure followed by charcoal and kerosene respectively. When the expenditure elasticity is less than one, there is weak reference for demand by a particular household. This leads to less consumption of energy items by such household.

The estimates of income elasticity are yielded by multiplying the estimated expenditure elasticities with the responsiveness of expenditure on energy items by income change from Engel's curve. All the estimates of income elasticities show that all the energy items are normal and necessity goods.

Table 6: Elasticity for energy consumption

Commodity	Mean budget share %	Expenditure elasticity	Income elasticity
Electricity	17.4	0.999	0.134
Kerosene	36.1	0.738	0.098
Charcoal	46.5	0.812	0.108

Source: Field Survey, 2009.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

The study reveals that kerosene is the most highly consumed energy source and the reason for preferring this energy source is its accessibility in the study area. The results also revealed that the entire energy source is price inelastic. The income elasticities were income inelastic in nature.

As income increases especially in the public sector, energy prices will also increase. Therefore, effort should be made to develop the energy sector of the economy as this will always cushion the effect of any wage increase.

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